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Urban Identity Formation in Light Characteristics of Future Cities

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Abstract

With the beginning of the 21st century and with the increase of urban growth in cities, the impact on urban cities significantly, especially environmental changes, climate, social and economic, which loss of some cities urban identity, As planners and designers of cities, we must facing these challenges by identifying the characteristics of future cities to Conservation our identity.

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Keywords

Urban Identity(UI) — Urban Form(UF) — Future Cities Characteristics(FCC)

1. Introduction

There are factors that have led to qualitative change in cities, Such as industrialization, globalization and technological developments, which affect the function and formation of cities, and affect the form of aesthetic and urban, which affect the urban identity.

There are some of future trends to build the cities, each with its characteristics and components. This is our role as planners and designers to build cities. We define these characteristics and how they reflect on the urban structure and the architectural identity such as formation of buildings, streets, public transport, landscape elements and urban spaces.

1.1. Problematic Search:

Urban Identity Formation (UIF) and affected Future Cities Characteristics (FCC)

1.2. Main Question:

How urban identity is formed by the characteristics of future city trends?

1.3. Research objectives:

Identity the characteristics of future city.

Formation of architectural identity.

1.4. Research methodology:

Research methodology is three stages the first stage study of urban identity through urban identity definition, urban identity elements, and urban identity (past, present) using inductive method, the second phase analysis future cities trends such as green city, smart city, social city, recreation city, touristic city, mixed city, science city and economic city, using analytical method, third stage show some leading Models for future cities to reach Future Cities Characteristics and Future urban identity using synthesis method.

2. Part I : Urban Identity(UI)

2.1. Urban identity concept

The word “identity” is generally described as a collection of features that serve to define any object. In addition, urban identity is defined as the natural and artificial elements of a city, its social, cultural and historical characteristics. Among these characteristics, the most obvious and impressive are the identity of that city. Every feature that differentiates one city from the other and appears differently is counted as the identity component of that city. Each of the cities has had an identity over time, and today they are remembered and living with the identities they have created. The identity of a city has its own characteristics with many factors (Simonovic, 2013).

Urban identity is defined by the identity of the place, the urban character, the character of the neighborhood and local character, Urban identity is concerned some of the sciences such as urban planning, urban design, landscape, environmental psychology, sociology and urban sociology, the identity of the place is also defined urban pattern and architecture style.

Urban identity science has become an important issue in the past 25 years, reflecting the culture of society and societies and how it reflects on urbanization.

Social events and social groups affect the form of urban identity in terms of gender, ethnicity, social class, religion and color to form the city of spaces, squares and streets, the urban identity is a reflection of the socio-economic and environmental needs of any society (Westminster, 2013).

Urban identity can also be defined (Cities of the future, 2015):

- The privacy of the place
- Local heritage
- Community culture
- Local urban pattern
- Local architectural character
- Building materials
- Environmentally appropriate urbanization
- Appropriate activities

2.2. Urban Identity Components

The identity of the city belongs to the city itself, which makes the city different from the others and adds value to that city and is the whole of the city-specific components. These components are also important features in the formation of that city’s identity. Concepts that constitute urban identity are gathered under two main headings as environmental and social identity. The relationships and interactions of these concepts forming urban identity (Parente, 2016).

Figure 1. Urban Identity Components

2.3. Urban identity (past, present)

Every place has a distinctive urban and architectural identity, be the attraction for residents or from outside, and then the urban and architectural identity becomes an engine of economic activity and source of income for the population, it produces architectural and urban identity of heritage and architecture grows and accumulates proceeds over the years, heritage consists of a set of cultural, social and environmental variables and economic as well as in the field of construction, and architectural identity and physical characteristics rooted in place, it's tied to him and gives him a special form, show urban identity through formed urban fabric buildings and surrounding spaces (squares, roads and parks and other spaces, building forms, designs, colors of buildings, architectural elements, and materials (, architectural or urban identity to be more explicit and prominent in president and large buildings (religious, governmental office, business and leisure), such models become a symbol for the place or city, the architectural and urban identity gives the place its spirit and taste,

Which required the architects and developers of urban and architectural identity confirmation, in distracts, streets, open spaces and buildings.

With the passage of time are affected by urban identity variables, technology and globalization and industrialization up to losing you physical identity, (Ozaslan, 1995) for example Cairo city - Egypt and Damascus city — Syria.

Cairo city past:

Cairo city present:

Figure 2. New Urban Identity for Cairo (past — present)

Damascus past:

Damascus present:

Figure 3. New Urban Identity for Damascus (past –present)

3. Part II: Future Cities Trends (FCT)

3.1. Future cities — importance and relevance

More than 70% of the populations live in cities; urbanization has become a major contributor to economic, demographic, social and environmental change, urbanization models have traditionally been applied without taking into account future results.

Today we see models of urban planning formed as a result of environmental, social and economic reasons without taking into account future results, this led to the incompatibility of urban urbanization with the predictions of the future, and total reliance on vehicle traffic has become the dominant belief in the 21st century, there should be integrated environmental management to increase welfare, prosperity and social cohesion to improve living and raise standards of quality of life to increase satisfaction with urbanization, environmental management provides appropriate funding resources and catalyzes investment to create fast, appropriate urban and environmental fabric to improve urbanization (Saglik & Kelkit, 2017).

3.2. Future cities — conceptions of success

There are some ideas, terminology and words that formed the concept of the future cities, they can be divided to environmental, social, economic and governmental, these characteristics and concepts was devised to satisfy future cities, they reflect different stakeholder and interest group conceptions of the ideal city of the future, These terms formed the urban identity of cities such as (Sustainable, Compact, Smart, Participative, Walkable, Integrated, Livable, Competitive, Productive, Innovative, Managed, Productive, Efficient... and so on), (Erdogan & Ayatac, 2015).

Table 1 Explains a some of the elements, terms and conceptions of success which are most used by those working in specific city-related fields, or concerned with particular future city outcomes.

Table 1. Elements, terms and conceptions of success

Environmental terms	Social terms	Economic terms	Governance terms
Garden	Participative	Entrepreneurial	Managed

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Table 1 continued

Sustainable	Walkable	Competitive	Intelligent
Eco	Integrated	Productive	Productive
Green	Inclusive	Innovative	Efficient
Compact	Just	Business friendly	Well-run, well-led
Smart	Open	Global	Smart
Resilient	Liveable	Resilient	Future

3.3. Identity and characteristics of future cities

The Global Human Settlements Report 2009 entitled "Sustainable city planning" includes an assessment of the effectiveness of urban planning systems as a tool to address the challenges facing cities in the twenty-first century. The most prominent part of this global report revolves around the need to change existing planning methodologies in most parts of the world, (Haapala, 1998).

- Smart city
- Green city
- Social city
- Recreation city
- Touristic city
- Mixed city
- Science city
- Economic city

Table 2. Smart city - Identity and characteristics

Definition of smart cities and Identity			
Smart City seeks to create a technological environment that provides telecommunications and innovative services and enables them to access any application, anywhere, anytime			
Smart Governance	Smart Grid	Smart Economy	Smart Mobility
Virtual citizen center	Flexible electric network	Flexible real estate	Car sharing management
Participation administration	Communication between electricity producer, consumer and energy storage	Networking local enterprises	Parking management
Information		Flexible exchange of data and goods	Integrated public transport system

Table 3. Green city - Identity and characteristics

Definition of green cities and Identity
Green City is a city that relies on renewable energy and clean technologies to achieve a carbon-free city and waste with the use of sustainable transportation.

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Table 3 continued

Zero Carbon City	Zero Waste City	Energy Generation	Transportation
Reliance on clean energy	Reduce consumption	100% Renewable Energy Solutions	green city based city to operate without fossil fueled vehicles
Reliance on fossil fuels	Recycle 90% of grey water	Solar system energy	High technology
Modern technologies	Reduce water leakage to 3%	Wind system energy	

Table 4. Social city - Identity and characteristics

Social city - Identity and characteristics	
The social city is a city based on the creation of a social environment among its inhabitants creating a formation of a range of spaces, gardens and spiritual and spiritual uses	
Community	Society
Integration and interaction	Social administration and governance
Free time activities for all generations	Social organization of the city and the people
Community gardens and spaces	Participation of the during an planning process
Family friendly places	
Public spaces for social integration	

Table 5. Recreation city - Identity and characteristics

Recreation city - Identity and characteristics		
The recreation city is a city based on nature in creating activities for entertainment, entertainment and sports activities to achieve the highest efficiency of calm, enjoyment and relaxation		
Silence and nature	Leisure and entertainment	Activity and sport
Places for contemplative and self-centered recreation	Cultural facilities	Exercising , walking , biking
Park	Spa/ wellness centers	Bike routes , hiking trails
Wind landscape area with lonely places	Playing, consuming	sport facilities indoors and outdoors
	Animation	

Table 6. Touristic city - Identity and characteristics

Touristic city - Identity and characteristics			
The tourist city depends on the exploitation of natural resources and cultural heritage to settle tourist activity that helps attract domestic and foreign tourists.			
Natural resources	Local attractions	Economic values	Cultural heritage
Unique landscape	Traditional building	Accommodation	Build heritage
Natural features	Traditional festivals	Hotels	Customs
Climates	Religion places	Souvenirs	traditions
	Environmental touristic	Restaurants	

Table 7. Mixed city — Identity and characteristics

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Table 7 continued

Mixed city - Identity and characteristics		
The mixed city depends on the multiplicity and confusion between the uses of land in the same neighborhood to reduce the travel distances between work, housing and shopping.		
Mix of functions	Mobility mix	Mixed generations
Short distance between housing , working , leisure , food supply	Interaction of different mobility systems	Cooperation between younger and older citizens
Balance utilization of infrastructure	Public transportation	Multi generation homes
	Private transportation	Demographic change
	Bike way and walking	

Table 8. Science city - Identity and characteristics

Science city - Identity and characteristics		
The scientific city relies on research centers, universities and technology industries to attract the largest number of researchers and scientists in the world.		
Schools and university	Research and industries	conventions
Schools and universities the core of science: they attract researchers and students from all over the world and spread of knowledge over the city.	Private companies may benefit from the neighboring researchers in the universities and may support them or cooperate	Conventions are good occasions to bring all participants of the science city together and invite researchers and partner from abroad

Table 9. Economic city - Identity and characteristics

Economic city - Identity and characteristics		
The economic city depends on the stability and improvement of the administrative conditions of the state through the exploitation of mineral resources in order to improve the living conditions of society.		
Good general framework	Stability	Economic values
National and international connectivity	Social stability	Raw materials
Efficient information system	Balanced social mixture	Accommodation
Administrative conditions	Good living conditions for the people at the merger of society	Hotels
		Restaurants

4. Part III: Urban Identity Model (UIM)

4.1. Msheireb Project- Doha- Qatar : Regeneration and a New Urban Identity (Aziz & Misni, 2016).

In 2008, the Msheireb project was launched over an area of 35 hectares; the aim of the project is to bring back the Qatari families to downtown Doha after their massive departure to the periphery during the 1950s and 60s. Beside aimed to improve the environment and boost the economy of the area. In short, the following are the main objectives of the master plan.

- To promote a sustainable way of living within a compact city framework that reduces automobile usage, increases density and promotes public transport and mixed use
- To renew a piece of city infrastructure so as to reduce its reliance on fossil fuel
- To promote better integrated social communities at the heart o the city where locals and expatriate workers

are walk able neighborhoods, public spaces and amenities

- To modernize a piece of Qatar’s capital city in ways that will resonate with local history and cultures.

In order to implement these objectives a number of modernization challenges are in this master plan(European Union, 2016).

- The short-term profit driven motives
- Fragmented land ownership and its impact on the development pattern
- Local climate and its impact on movement and urban form
- The loss of community spirit and identity in the process of modernization
- Image of the city-creation not transposition.
- To implement these objectives the master plan proposed a safe and a thriving residential /commercial center containing facilities and amenities within a walk able distance (Boussaa, 2017).
- In Msheireb, streets and neighborhoods form a compact urban pattern rather than being scattered each one in its own plot. The compact layout offers many advantages in terms of creating shaded streets that encourage inhabitants to walk.
- This compact urban pattern is inspired from the old neighborhoods, as a response to climatic and social considerations. In addition, it encourages the social interaction between neighbors that will eventually increase the sense of place and identity.
- Msheireb is structured around five main districts that encourage social interaction. These districts consist of the Emiri Diwan Quarter, which will host the National Guard and other services supporting the Emiri Diwan. A second district, the Mixed-Use and Residential Quarter, adjacent to the commercial quarter. It contains the main plaza to be the main breathing element for the entire Msheireb area, residential buildings, offices and other dynamic activities. A third district, the Retail Quarter, is the largest district, which comprises the most luxurious spaces in the project and city of Doha. The fourth district, the Business Gateway Quarter, is a business-oriented quarter full of business opportunities and governmental representatives o facilitate future investments in the city. The heritage Quarter, which escaped miraculously from decimation, forms the fifth part and stands as the only physical witness of the past. It is the main gateway to Msheireb and acts as the catalyst to create a new urban identity for the entire district.
- The need to establish a new urban identity and character for Msheireb was fundamental in creating a new image to the city. Instead of transcribing from the past, influences are inspired from studying the local built heritage. Lessons learn from an examination of the historic districts in Doha and AlWakra enabled the establishment of seven principles as a guide for the design of the master plan, timelessness, diversity and unity, form and geometry, aspect of home, aspect of street, designing for climate and elements of architecture These principles intend to ease life for the future inhabitants while they provide them with a new urban identity inspired but not copied from the past.
- The heritage quarter is the only survivor heritage area in Msheireb, the quarter represents an area equivalent to 2% of the entire 35 ha sites. The heritage quarter has two main roles, first it functions as the main Msheireb’s entrance, to welcome the local and global visitors from the adjacent Souk Waqif. Secondly, it provides a cultural trail to retrace Qatar’s history before 1950.
- One way of rediscovering the urban identity of the city of Doha is to go back to its first roots and try to sustain them in face of the emerging global environments. Through the Msheireb urban regeneration project.

Figure 4. New Urban Identity - Msheireb Project- Doha- Qatar

5. Conclusion

Through observation and analysis of the characteristics and identity of the future cities (green cities — smart cities — mixed cities — economic cities — social and scientific cities — recreational -tourist cities) and compare them with the concept of urban identity and components we find that:

- Urban identity means (place — privacy — heritage — culture — past — urban compatibility — simulation)
- There are properties to future cities can reflect urban identity of our cities as follows :
- **The identity of green cities** (climate and environmental adjustment — green urbanize — urban fabric — local architectural character -sustainable transport)
- **The Identity of smart cities** (Participation administration — Information — Flexible exchange of data and goods-Car sharing management-Integrated public transport system)
- **The Identity of social cities** (Integration and interaction — Free time activities for all generations — Community gardens and spaces — Family friendly places — Public spaces for social integration — Social organization of the city and the people — Participation of the during a planning process)

- **The Identity of Recreation cities** (Cultural facilities — Spa/ wellness centers — Playing, consuming — Animation — Exercising, walking, biking — Bike routes, hiking trails, sport facilities indoors and outdoors)
- **The Identity of Touristic cities** (Unique landscape — Natural features — Climates — Build heritage — Customs and traditions — Traditional building — Traditional festivals — Religion places — Environmental touristic — Accommodation — Hotels — Souvenirs — Food — Restaurants)
- **The Identity of mixed cities** (Short distances between housing, working, leisure, food supply — Balance utilization of infrastructure — Cooperation between younger and older citizens — Multi generation homes — Demographic change — Interaction of different mobility systems — Public transportation — Private transportation — Bike way — walking)
- **The Identity of Science cities** (Schools and universities the core of science: they attract researchers and students from all over the world and spread of knowledge over the city -. Private companies may benefit from the neighboring researchers in the universities and may support them or cooperate)
- **The Identity of economic cities** (National and international connectivity- Efficient information system — Administrative conditions - Social stability — Balanced social mixture — Good living conditions for the people at the merger of society)

6. References:

1. Haapala, A. (1998). Strangeness and familiarity in the urban environment. – e City as Cultural Metaphor. In *Studies in Urban Aesthetics. International Institute, 1998.*
2. Aziz, N., & Misni, A. (2016). 'Open Space And Urban Identity. *Sustainable Cities, Healthy Communities, 74-76.*
3. Boussaa, D. (2017). Urban Regeneration and the Search for Identity in Historic Cities. *Sustainability, 10(1), 1-16.*
4. Erdogan, B. D., & Ayatac, H. (2015). " Assessment of urban identity characteristics in public places: A case study of Ortakoy Square. *ITU Journal of the Faculty of Architecture, 12(1), 115-125.*
5. Cities of the future. (2015). Cities of the future - global competition, local leadership – 2005. Retrieved from: www.pwc.com/government.
6. Ozaslan, N. (1995). *Historic urban fabric: Source of inspiration for contemporary city form*(PhD thesis, University of York, 1995). Heslington, York: University of York.
7. Parente, M. (2016). Designing the City Identity: Strategic and Product Design for New Experiential Ways of Living, Enabling, and Interacting with the Urban Context. *Design Management Journal, 10(1), 62-71*
8. Saglik, E., & Kelkit, A. (2017). Evaluation of Urban Identity and its Components in Landscape Architecture. *Journal of Landscape Architecture Research, 1(1), 36-39.*
9. Simonovic, D. (2013). Rehabilitation of Urban Identity of Cities in the Banja Luka Region through Urban Form Regulation. *SPATIUM International Review, December 2013, pp. 28-32.*
10. European Union. (2016). The European Economic and Social Committee. In *Culture, Cities and Identity in Europe.*
11. Westminster. (2013). Westminster Comprehensive Plan –City Identity and Design.